

On fuzzy α -open sets in generalized fuzzy topological spaces

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ABSTRACT : In this paper, we have studied the notion of fuzzy α -open sets in generalized fuzzy topological spaces. We have established some significant properties of g -fuzzy α -open sets. We have also constructed elementary examples which are useful in the theory of g -fuzzy α -open sets in generalized fuzzy topological spaces.

KEY WORDS: Fuzzy topology, Generalized fuzzy topology, g -fuzzy open sets, g -fuzzy α -open sets.

1. INTRODUCTION : The concept of fuzzy sets was introduced by L.A. Zadeh [9] in 1965. Fuzzy sets are generalization of abstract sets or crisp sets. They have a much wider scope in solving various kind of real world physical problems. Fuzzy sets provide a natural foundation for introducing new branch of mathematics namely fuzzy topology.

The theory of fuzzy topological spaces has grown as an active field of mathematical research in recent times. The concept of fuzzy topological space was first introduced in 1968 by C.L. Chang [4]. Later on many mathematicians contributed in the development of the theory of fuzzy topological spaces.

Various generalized forms of fuzzy open sets in fuzzy topological spaces were introduced by the researchers. In 1981 K.K. Azad [1] has introduced the concept of fuzzy semi-open sets in fuzzy topological spaces. Bin Shahana in 1991 [2] has introduced the concept of fuzzy pre-open sets and fuzzy α -open

sets in fuzzy topological space. S.S.Thakur in 1998 [8] has introduced the concept of fuzzy semi pre-open sets in fuzzy topological spaces. In this paper we have studied the concept of fuzzy α -open set in the category of Generalized fuzzy topological spaces.

2. PRELIMINARIES :

Proposition 2.1 : Let X be a Universal crisp set A fuzzy set on X is a map

$\lambda : X \rightarrow I$, where $I = [0,1]$. Suppose $\{\lambda_j : X \rightarrow I\}_{j \in J}$, where J is an index set, is

any family of fuzzy sets on X . Then union of fuzzy sets λ_j , is the fuzzy

set $\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j : X \rightarrow I$ and is defined as $(\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j)(x) = \sup \{\lambda_j(x) : j \in J\}$, for all

$x \in X$. The intersection of the fuzzy sets $\lambda_j, j \in J$ is the fuzzy set $\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j : X \rightarrow I$

and is defined as $(\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j)(x) = \inf \{\lambda_j(x) : j \in J\}$, for all $x \in X$. If

$\lambda, \mu : X \rightarrow I$, are two fuzzy sets on X then λ is said to be **subset** of μ if

$\lambda(x) \leq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. the **complement** of a fuzzy set λ is denoted by

λ^c and is defined as $\lambda^c(x) = 1 - \lambda(x), \forall x \in X$.

Definition 2.1 [4] Let X be a (non-empty) universal crisp set. A generalized **fuzzy topology** on X is a non empty collection τ_g of fuzzy sets on X satisfying the following conditions :

- (i) Fuzzy sets **0** and **1** belong to τ_g .
- (ii) Any arbitrary union of members of τ_g is in τ_g .

Here **0** and **1** represent the **Zero Fuzzy Set** and the **Whole Fuzzy set** on X , defined as, $0(x) = 0$, and $1(x) = 1$, for all $x \in X$. The pair (X, τ_g) is called

Generalized Fuzzy Topological Space. For Convenience, we shall denote the generalized fuzzy topological space simply by X .

Example 2.2 Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5\}$ be the Universal crisp set and $A, B: X \rightarrow I$ be two fuzzy sets in X , defined as :

$$A = \{(x_1, 0.5), (x_2, 0.7), (x_3, 0.9), (x_4, 0.2), (x_5, 0.4)\} \text{ and}$$

$$B = \{(x_1, 0.4), (x_2, 0.3), (x_3, 0.9), (x_4, 0.5), (x_5, 0.6)\}.$$

Then clearly

$C \equiv A \cup B = \{(x_1, 0.5), (x_2, 0.7), (x_3, 0.9), (x_4, 0.5), (x_5, 0.6)\}$ we see that collection $\tau_g = \{0, A, B, C, 1\}$ satisfies two conditions of g -fuzzy topology on X .

Hence (X, τ_g) is a g -fuzzy topological space.

Definition 2.3 Let (X, τ_g) be a generalized fuzzy topological space. The members of the collection τ_g are called **g -fuzzy open sets** and the complement of g -fuzzy open sets are called g -fuzzy closed sets. For a fuzzy set A in X **the closure of A** is denoted by $Cl(A)$ and is defined as $Cl(A) = \inf\{K : A \subseteq K, K^C \in \tau_g\}$. The **interior A** is denoted by $Int(A)$ and is defined as $Int(A) = \sup\{Q : Q \subseteq A, Q \in \tau_g\}$.

Remark 2.1: In a generalized fuzzy topological space (X, τ_g) for a fuzzy set A in X . We note that $Cl(A)$ equals to the intersection of all g -fuzzy closed sets in X containing A . Thus $Cl(A)$ is the smallest g -fuzzy closed sets in X containing A . Further we note that $Int(A)$ equals to the union of all g -fuzzy open sets in X contained in A . Thus $Int(A)$ is the largest g -fuzzy open set in X contained in A .

Proposition 2.2 Let (X, τ_g) be a g -fuzzy topological space. Then Arbitrary intersection of g -fuzzy closed sets in X is a g -fuzzy closed set in X .

Theorem 2.1 Let (X, τ_g) be a g -fuzzy topological space and let A be a fuzzy set in X . Then

(i) $Cl(A)=A$ if and only if A is a g -fuzzy closed set in X .

(ii) $Int(A)=A$ if and only if A is a g -fuzzy open set in X .

Proposition 2.3 Let (X, τ_g) be a g -fuzzy topological space and let A be a fuzzy set in X . Then (i) $Cl(A^c) = (Int(A))^c$ and (ii)

$$Int(A^c) = (Cl(A))^c.$$

Proof :(i) Let A be the fuzzy set in X . Suppose that the family of all fuzzy open set in contained in given by $\{A_j : A_j \subseteq A, A_j \in \tau, \forall j \in J\}$ Clearly since $A_j \subseteq A \forall A_j$, taking complement, we have $A^c \subseteq A_j^c \forall A_j, j \in J$ Further we observe that $int(A) = \cup_{j \in J} A_j$ and hence $(int(A))^c = 1 - \cup_{j \in J} A_j = (\cup_{j \in J} A_j)^c = \cap_{j \in J} A_j^c$ where $\{A_j^c\}$ is the family of fuzzy closed set contained in A^c Therefore is $\cap_{j \in J} A_j^c$ the closure of the fuzzy set A^c Therefore $(int(A))^c = \cap_{j \in J} A_j^c = Cl(A^c)$ hence $Cl(A^c) = (Int(A))^c$

Proof: (ii) Consider the family $\{K_j\}_{j \in J}$ of all fuzzy closed sets containing A in X , so that $Cl(A) = \inf\{K_j : K_j \supset A \text{ and } K_j \text{ is closed } \forall j \in J\} = \cap_{j \in J} K_j$ hence $(Cl(A))^c = (\cap_{j \in J} K_j)^c = \cup_{j \in J} K_j^c$ then clearly and is fuzzy open set .therefore $\{K_j^c\}_{j \in J}$ is a family of all open sets contained in hence $\cup_{j \in J} K_j^c = int(A^c)$ so prove that $Int(A^c) = (Cl(A))^c$

Theorem 2.2 (X, τ_g) be a g -fuzzy topological space and let $\{\lambda_j\}_{j \in J}$ be any arbitrary collection of fuzzy sets in X . Then

(i) $Int(\cup_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \geq \cup_{j \in J} Int(\lambda_j)$ and

(ii) $Cl(\cup_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \geq \cup_{j \in J} Cl(\lambda_j)$.

3. g-Fuzzy α -Open Sets- In this section we have studied elementary peroperties of g -fuzzy α -open sets. The definition of g -fuzzy α -open set is follows:

Definition 3.1 : Let (X, τ_g) be a g -fuzzy topological space and $\lambda : X \rightarrow I$ be a

fuzzy set in X . Then λ is said to be g -fuzzy α -open set in X if $\lambda \leq \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(\text{Int}(\lambda)))$.

Proposition 3.2 : In a g -fuzzy topological space every g -fuzzy open set is g -fuzzy α -open. However the converse need not be true, i.e. a g -fuzzy α -open set may not be g -fuzzy open.

Proof : Let X be a g -fuzzy topological space and let λ be a g -fuzzy open set in X . Then $\text{Int}(\lambda) = \lambda$. Since $\lambda \leq \text{Cl}(\lambda)$, we have $\lambda \leq \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(\lambda))$. This implies, $\lambda = \text{Int}(\lambda) \leq \text{Int}(\text{Cl}(\text{Int}(\lambda)))$. Hence λ is a g -fuzzy open set in X .

The converse of proposition 3.1 is not necessarily true. We have following example :

Example 3.3 Let us consider the generalized fuzzy topological space X in example 2.2 The fuzzy set $D = \{(x_1, 0.6), (x_2, 0.7), (x_3, 0.9), (x_4, 0.6), (x_5, 0.7)\}$ is a g -fuzzy α -open set in X but not a g -fuzzy open set in X .

Theorem - 3.4 : In a g -fuzzy topological space arbitrary union of g -fuzzy α -open sets is g -fuzzy α -open set is g -fuzzy α -open set.

Proof: Let X be a g -fuzzy topological space and let $\{\lambda_j\}_{j \in J}$ be a family of g -fuzzy α -open sets in X then for each $j \in J$, $\lambda_j \leq \text{int}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(\lambda_j)))$ Substituting $\lambda = \cup_{j \in J} \lambda_j$ we have $\text{int}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(\lambda))) = \text{int}(\text{cl}(\text{int}(\cup_{j \in J} \lambda_j))) \geq \text{int}(\text{cl}(\cup_{j \in J} \lambda_j \text{int} \lambda_j)) \geq \text{int}(\cup_{j \in J} \text{cl}(\text{int}(\lambda_j))) \geq \cup_{j \in J} \text{int}(\text{cl}(\text{int} \lambda_j)) \geq \cup_{j \in J} \lambda_j = \lambda$ Thus λ is a g -fuzzy α -open set in x .

Definition 3.5 Let X be g -fuzzy topological space. A fuzzy set $x_r : X \rightarrow 1$ where $x \in X$ and $0 < r \leq 1$, is said to be a fuzzy point in a fuzzy topological space X if.

$$x_r(y) = \begin{cases} r, & \text{if } y = x; \\ 0, & \text{if } y \neq x, y \in X \end{cases}$$

The fuzzy point x_r belongs to a fuzzy set λ in X if $r \leq \lambda(x)$ i.e., x_r is a subset of λ .

Proposition 3.6 Let X be a g -fuzzy topological space. A fuzzy set λ is g -fuzzy α -open in X if for each fuzzy point $x_r \in \lambda$ there exists a g -fuzzy α -open set μ in X such that $x_r \in \mu$ and $\mu \leq \lambda$.

Proof : Let λ be g -fuzzy α -open set in X . If x_r is a fuzzy point in X and $x_r \in \lambda$, then clearly that g -fuzzy α -open set λ itself satisfies the desired condition. Conversely suppose λ is a fuzzy set in X having the property that for each fuzzy point $x_r \in \lambda$, $x \in X$ there exists g -fuzzy α -open set say μ_x in X such that $x_r \in \mu_x$ and $\mu_x \leq \lambda$. Then by proposition 3.4, we deduce that $\mu = \bigcup_{x \in X} \mu_x$ is g -fuzzy α -open set in X satisfying the desired condition.

Definition 3.7 Let X be a g -fuzzy topological space and $\lambda: X \rightarrow 1$ be a fuzzy set in X . then λ is said to be g -fuzzy α -closed set if λ^c is a g -fuzzy α -open set in X .

Remark : From Proposition 3.2 it follow that every g -fuzzy closed set in X is g -fuzzy α -closed set but the converse is not necessarily true.

Proposition 3.8 In a g -fuzzy topological space arbitrary intersection of g -fuzzy α -closed sets is g -fuzzy α -closed

Proof : Let X be a g -fuzzy topological space and let $\{\lambda_j\}_{j \in J}$ be a family of g -fuzzy α -open sets in X . Then $\{\lambda_j^c\}_{j \in J}$ is a family of g -fuzzy α -closed sets in X . From theorem 3.4 we note that $\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j^c = (\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j)^c$ is a g -fuzzy α -open set in X . Hence $\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j$ is a g -fuzzy α -closed set in X .

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